

Recommended citation: Shaw, C., Kloot, B., & Ahmed, N. (2021). Re-imagining engineering education in South Africa. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 491-499). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14647079.

RE-IMAGINING ENGINEERING EDUCATION IN SOUTH AFRICA

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Conference Key Areas: *Accessibility, participation and inclusion; Curriculum development*

Keywords: *Transformative learning, student engagement, engineering identity.*

ABSTRACT

The challenge presented by the global pandemic has brought into focus the need for curricula that stimulate an awareness of the complexity of society. Engineering graduates need to be more conscious of and have better access to contextual knowledge and expertise beyond the technical. As a way of providing such access, an 'Engineer in Society' course has been offered to third-year mechanical engineering students at the University of Cape Town.

The sudden shift from in-person to online learning in 2020 due to the Covid-19 exacerbated student differences and curtailed student engagement and participation. As restrictions ease in South Africa and physically-distanced meetings become possible, we draw on Mezirow's theory of transformative learning to explore the impact of the course on how engineering students think about society. According to Mezirow, transformative learning takes place when the assumptions underpinning one's frame of reference are changed. The study engaged with this by asking a twofold research question: How did students experience engagement within the course and what sorts of transformations did they experience?

We found qualitatively different ways in which students engaged with course content, engagement with peers and others, and engagement with the delivery modes of the

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course. Students experienced shifts or transformations in the understanding of their professional identity with the recognition of multiple possible engineering identities; professional responsibility in the form of awareness of active roles in relation to environmental and social issues; and epistemological shifts from abstract, decontextualised knowledge to practical, contextual knowledge.

1 INTRODUCTION

The argument for the inclusion of knowledge and skills for the development of engineering graduates who can engage with their role in relation to social responsibility has been well documented. Such knowledge and skills are often presented in courses and modules that draw on humanities, the social sciences, communication and management disciplines, and are either offered as electives or part of the core curriculum. These might be called ‘non-technical’ (Florman, 1997) courses, liberal arts courses or, in the South African context ‘complementary studies’. Much debate has also been raised as to who should provide such offerings, with engineering academic staff being favoured over disciplinary experts.

Unlike other professions (such as law and medicine), engineers rarely have a direct relationship with society. Rather, Aslaksen (2015) suggests that the organisations within the industries that employ engineers mediate their relationship with society. However, registration as a professional engineer requires that individuals subscribe to a code of conduct that governs their practice and they can hence be held accountable for their conduct with respect to social, environmental and general ethical engagements. Engineering graduates therefore need to have a clear understanding of the complexity of their role within and their responsibility toward society. In different contexts, undergraduate engineering curricula have, in numerous ways, tried to incorporate non-technical content that introduces engineering students to social, political, environmental, economic and ethical issues with varied success.

What does it mean for us, as engineering educators, to build engineering capacity for effective interaction with society and develop graduate attributes appropriate for ethical economic development? Could we successfully re-imagine engineering education in South Africa and in doing so produce future-focussed graduates who can drive positive change? To initiate this ambitious aim, this paper specifically focuses on how students in a complementary studies course (entitled Engineer in Society) experience engagement and the extent to which their perspectives were transformed in the context of in-person and online learning. This study addresses the twofold research question: How did students experience engagement within the course and what sorts of transformations did they experience?

1.1 The context for the study

The University of Cape Town (UCT) is a research-intensive institution with a set of established undergraduate engineering programmes. As part of a comprehensive re-curriculation exercise in the Department of Mechanical Engineering, two of the authors were tasked with renewing complementary studies courses in the department. The long-standing courses that fulfilled this role were quite narrow and dealt with the topics of engineering professionalism, project management and the

environment. With the intention of making the new offerings more holistic and relevant, two larger follow-on courses were developed. The first was a third-year course that was designed to be *outward-looking* in that it addressed issues relating to the role of the engineer in society (broadly speaking). The second course was to be offered in fourth year and was to be *inward-looking*, i.e. focusing on the role of the engineer within organisations and the business workplace.

The outward-looking course was named 'Engineer in Society' in reference to the seminal work by Mills (1946). This course was designed as a whole-year course worth 16 credits (designed to take the average student 160 hours to complete). It was offered for the first time in 2020 and is the focus of this paper. The inward-looking course was named 'Engineer in Business' and was a semester course but worth the same credits as Engineer in Society. This course is being offered for the first time in 2021.

1.2 The structure of the Engineer in Society course

It was decided to divide the content of the Engineer in Society course into four modules, each dealing with an aspect of society: human society, the biophysical environment, economic systems and political structures. One of the primary objectives of this course was to provide the opportunity for the students to engage with a plurality of perspectives and to develop a critical awareness of the role of engineering – and engineers – in society. This was facilitated by including field trips to sites of social and political importance, bringing in guest lecturers from industry and having regular group work sessions. The learning activities directed students towards reflection and discussion to deepen their thinking about complex issues in all realms of society.

The course was structured so that about 40% of students' time was to be spent in lectures and tutorials. This was to include two 45-minute lectures a week with afternoon tutorial every two weeks. About 25% of students' time was to be spent engaging with readings or video documentaries. Two field trips were planned which were to take 10% of the course time. The remainder of the time was to be dedicated to assessment activities such as reports, writing essays and taking tests. We thought it appropriate that the most important assessment was a capstone essay which required the students to reflect on the course and make explicit links between the modules.

1.3 The shift to online teaching and learning

The Covid-19 pandemic took hold in South Africa in mid-March of 2020. UCT decided to close for the mid-semester vacation one week early and this marked the end of in-person learning. As the country went into 'lockdown', the university prolonged the vacation and only opened again in mid-April for online learning. Given problems with access to technology and bandwidth for some students, UCT decided that lectures were to be presented asynchronously. There was no doubt that the move to the online environment exacerbated student differences (Czerniewicz, e.al. 2020) and curtailed student engagement and participation. Indeed, students tended to be – and still are to some extent – more physically isolated from one another and

epistemologically insulated from perspectives outside an engineering curriculum that focuses on technical knowledge.

The shift to online mode impacted the structure of the course and the time that students spent on the various activities. The two 45-minute lectures were condensed into a single hour-long lecture (with PDF slides) that was released at the start of the week. In-person engagement was substituted by online forum discussions via the university's course management system. Other impacts were that the field trip in the latter part of the year had to be cancelled and guest speakers had to make online lecture videos where possible. These changes are described in more detail below.

2 CONCEPTUAL FRAMING

There are many perspectives that might be used to account for human experience in relation to others. For example, Christie (2005) emphasises how individual interests are in competition with – and often come at the expense of – a collective common good. Maistry (2014) goes further and suggests that the tension pervading higher education can be seen as capitalist market discourses in competition with social democratic citizenship discourses' (p. 57). In a higher education institution such as a university, the rhetoric aligned with capitalist market/neoliberal discourses places emphasis on, for example, institutional efficiency, rankings, test scores and work readiness of graduates and curricula that embrace skills and knowledge suitable for value creation in the form of profit. Courses that do not fit the mould of equipping graduates with technical knowledge and skills, such as complementary studies courses, are therefore afforded less legitimacy. Johnson, Lee and McGregor (1996) suggest that engineering knowledge contributes to this tension by setting up itself as a kind of 'captive discourse' that is intolerant of other forms of knowledge.

With regard to the student experience, the theoretical and analytical tools that we draw on provide a perspective on shifts in understanding as a consequence of engagement. Transformative learning theory (Mezirow, 1991) provides conceptual explanations for the shifts experienced as a consequence of learning. Mezirow (1991) points out that not all learning is transformative but when learning transforms, there is either change in beliefs or attitude, what Mezirow calls a meaning scheme, or our entire perspective can be transformed. According to Mezirow, every act of learning involves interpretation. Learning, in Mezirow's terms, would result in new or revised interpretations 'of the meaning of one's experience in order to guide future action' (1991, p. 12).

Sfard and Prusak (2005) take a different view of learning, characterising it as a culturally-shaped activity. They propose identity as the conceptual link between learning and its sociocultural context, with learning conceived of as 'closing the gap' between actual (e.g. engineering student) and designated (e.g. professional engineer) identities. The notion of learning as identity development is one that finds favour in a number of learning theories as it serves to account for a psycho-social view of learning, i.e. expanding the concept of learning to beyond the individual only and to account for the context or ways in which society influences that way individuals making meaning of their experiences as learning.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

This paper reports on the emergent findings of a larger research project that includes an investigation of the historical development of engineering in South Africa, student experiences of learning about South African society in the engineering curriculum, and recommendations for engagement with the engineering curriculum. For investigating the student experience, a qualitative research design was used to access in-depth perceptions of students' experiences of learning.

3.2 Data collection and analysis

Data was primarily drawn from semi-structured interviews using Microsoft Teams and was supported by data from two student course evaluations (see Table 1). All 117 students who were registered for the Engineer in Society course in 2020 were invited to participate in a 30-minute, online interview to reflect on their experience of the course. The author who was not involved in the teaching of the course conducted the interviews. Nineteen students responded and eighteen interviews were conducted. These students represented a purposive sample that included students from different schooling environments, demographics, nationality, gender, as well as a variety of achievement scores in course assessments.

Table 1: Data sources

Data source	No. of students participating (maximum 117)
Course evaluation, June 2020	28 students (24%)
Course evaluation, Nov 2020	29 students (25%)
Semi-structured interviews, June- July 2021	18 students (15%)

Data were analysed thematically using compare-and-contrast qualitative techniques. All the authors were involved in the analysis of the recorded interviews with at least two researchers reviewing each recording and transcription. The emergent themes identified by researchers were compared and final themes agreed upon.

4 FINDINGS

4.1. Engagement

Engagement with content

The formal course evaluations in the middle and at the end of the year suggested that most of the class were positively engaged. In the interviews, students also contrasted the course with regular undergraduate engineering courses that were described as 'involving calculations'. One student said that the course 'seemed different from your generic, just maths plug-and-chug courses so something different... "breath of fresh air" I guess you might call it' (Interview 7).

As expected, there were some negative comments about the course content, with students characterising it as ‘airy-fairy (Interview 6)’, a ‘Humanities-type course’ (Interview 8) or being akin to Life Orientation, a compulsory subject in secondary school in South Africa which tends to be derided because of its vague focus on life skills. Students who saw the course in this way were less engaged with the content. They described the lectures as ‘tedious’ and, even though they conceded that some of the content was new to them, characterised the course as being about general knowledge or ‘common knowledge’ (Interview 7), as one student put it.

Engagement with people

In line with the intentions of the course, we were pleased to see that students mentioned the value they found in learning from others. A number of students mentioned the afternoon visit to an area known as ‘District Six’ and its museum. This site is of political and social importance because its residents - about 60,000 of them - were forcibly removed by the apartheid government in the 1970s when it was declared a ‘whites only’ area. This visit involved hearing stories from some of the former residents who grew up in District Six and witnessed the forced removals.

Students mentioned the important role this experience played in ‘opening their eyes’ to what apartheid was like and its lasting impact on South African society.

Interestingly, one student highlighted how the visit actually gave her insight into the lives of her peers whose families were affected by the District Six removals. Indeed, learning from other students was seen to be a key ‘takeaway’ by some students (as the section below indicates). In this regard, the interviewees mentioned other students saying or posting things that made them reconsider their own point of view or other students recommending readings or videos that were relevant and interesting.

Another set of people that had a profound impact on students was the guest lecturers. One student mentioned that engagement with the guest lecturers really helped her to see that engineering is not ‘some untouchable industry’ but is made up of ordinary people:

...seeing the guest lecturers and seeing them as people... it really came to help me to understand that there has got to be a place where you are going to start and not everyone starts at the same pace (Interview 3).

Delivery of the course

Students’ perspectives on engagement were often linked to the mode of course delivery. Most students felt that they engaged better when the course was running in face-to-face or ‘in-person’ mode compared to when it was online. Activities such as tutorials (which often involved group work before the lockdown), field trips and class discussions were mentioned in this regard. One student suggested that the interactive nature of the course meant that it was especially affected by the pandemic:

...what spoiled the course is the fact that we moved to online learning and that kind of put a blow into power that the course had... this type of course is a very interactive course (Interview 5).

Interestingly, when students rated their involvement in the course in the formal course evaluation, they indicated little change before lockdown compared to afterwards. Furthermore, a student felt that her engagement actually improved in the online space. She said that she and her classmates felt quite shy in class and that discussions among them tended to be ‘surface-level’. But she explained that students tended to delve more deeply into issues when the course shifted online. This was in the context of students being required to post their opinions using a tool in the university online platform called *forums*: ‘...I think that everyone is much bolder if you have to type on the forums than raise your hand in class so I think I was very much engaged in the content post-Covid than before (Interview 1)’.

4.2 Transformations

Three themes emerged as transformations or shifts in perception as a consequence of participation in the course. They are described below.

Professional identity

This theme encompasses changes in perceptions of professional identity ranging from descriptions of how the course facilitated identification with the profession more closely – ‘I didn’t know what it meant to be an engineer before the course’ (interview 3) – to identifying the type of engineer they wanted to be, illustrated by the student in interview 4: ‘The course showed me that you can be philanthropic in your work as an engineer’. The breadth of the course content and the engagement with the diversity of people and activities were experienced by some students as possibilities for aligning their personal goals with professional goals. This was evident from the student in interview 4, who noted that ‘the course is refreshing, [it] showed me that I can integrate my passions with work’. For other students, engagement with the course facilitated a shift from theoretical, technical engineering concepts to pragmatic considerations of what becoming a practicing engineer could mean: ‘I could now see the difference between being an engineer and applied maths’ (Interview 3). The course can therefore be seen as successful in closing the gap between actual (e.g. engineering student) and designated (e.g. professional engineer) identities (Sfard and Prusak, 2005).

Professional responsibility

Interviewees reported a deeper understanding of the relevance of context in the practice of engineering, especially in relation to various aspects of society. This resulted in students gaining a sense of confidence in the discipline they had chosen to study: ‘It gave me a greater sense of duty... reinforced why I like engineering’ (Interview 3). The sense of purpose in relation to the country was echoed in interview 5: ‘I am proud of the Faculty I am in because it shows how important it is to keep the country running smoothly’.

The sense of social responsibility was not shared by all interviewees, a criticism from a student was that they perceived the course to have a social justice orientation that did not consider that new graduates would be powerless to go against decisions made by their employers and their responsibility would be to their bosses: ‘...money rules the world and ...engineers are slaves to the industry’ (Interview 8). This notion draws attention to the need to manage the tension between the capitalist market

discourses and social democratic citizenship discourses as noted by Maistry (2014), given the reality of the graduates' initial forays into engineering industries.

Epistemological shifts

The course presented the opportunity for students to 'have an open space to develop opinions' (Interview 4), the recognition that opinions supported by robust argument was valued as a contribution was a shift from perceptions of knowledge as binary, i.e. either right or wrong:

...it was not something that I was able to experience in my other courses because we kind of take... naturally like an engineer would do, we kind of take what is said as the truth and there is no questioning it... So there is not much engagement in any of my other courses so it was a really nice experience to be able to... to question the lecturer, to question your classmates... (Interview 1)

The awareness of plural forms of knowledge can be illustrated by the comment the students in interview 1, in which s/he described how his/her way of thinking was changed through dialogue with classmates which allowed her to be more open-minded and considerate: '...being open to learning from anywhere, considering different perspectives, making the world your classroom'. Such engagement led to an interrogation of personal biases towards certain issues that the student wasn't aware of until discussions with peers through online forums.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As reported in other studies, students' expectations were that with a non-technical course, they expected to do well without necessarily taking the course seriously. There were also students who struggled to engage with the course. On the other hand, there were students who really enjoyed the course, engaged with the content and embraced the learning opportunities the course provided. Both of these dispositions emerged strongly in the course evaluations and the interviews which suggests that the course had a polarising effect. Drawing on Johnston, Lee and McGregor (1996), it seemed that some students experienced a sort of 'epistemological conflict' as they encountered this course in the context of their third year of a predominantly technical degree. Exploring the deeper reasons for this is an ongoing interest in the broader project.

The few students who saw the course as illegitimate - very much the minority - also expressed that they did not learn very much. On the other hand, the students who engaged with the course tended to describe moments of transformative learning that suggests that their entire meaning scheme (Mezirow, 1991) was altered. This was particularly evident in the visit to District Six and - importantly - in their interactions with peers around the social issues involved. Drawing on Sfard and Prusak (2005), there is evidence that the cultural context shaped the development of conceptual understanding relating to engineering identity and the role of engineering in society. 'Cultural context' here does not only refer to the experience that students had on the field trip where they were exposed to the (romanticised) culture of the District Six that ceased to exist after the forced removals. Rather, it must be understood more broadly, even in terms of an online culture that can be enhanced to promote learning about self and others in a way that is not possible face to face.

The variety of modalities and opportunities was effective in facilitating active engagement, as students clearly favoured the class discussions, field trips and practitioner contributions. The contextualisation of engineering knowledge, in combination with opportunities for students to reflect on what engineering practice means for them allowed some students to re-interpret the meaning that they made of their experiences. While we hesitate to label such learning as transformative, we recognise that it should be explored further.

Going forward, we are challenged to try to find a way through student resistance to non-technical courses and design opportunities for learning that can contribute to transformative learning without risk of infection or transmission of the Covid-19 virus. At the same time, we recognise online learning can provide meaningful engagement. We are also cognizant of the need to manage the tension between characterisations of 'this is the way the world works in a capitalist economy' with social justice views of society.

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